

The Sanctuaries of the Egyptian Gods at Delos

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There are three sanctuaries dedicated to the Egyptian deities (Isis, Serapis, Anubis, Harpocrates, Osiris, Bubastis) in Delos. The first one is Sarapieion A and consists of a court and a small temple built on a vault accessible to water, two rooms of which one had benches, probably for the gatherings, and a portico. There is a long inscription known as the “chronic of the Sarapieion” and gives information about the origins of the sanctuary. According to this inscription, the founder of the sanctuary was the priest Apollonios; his grandfather Apollonios was the one who brought his god with him when he arrived from Memphis. Serapis appeared in a dream appointing where the sanctuary had to be built. It was probably private, and the office of the priest was hereditary. The Sarapieion B was not far from the previous one. It was constructed on a small terrace. It has been preserved only in ruins, and it once had a court, spaces with benches, a small temple, a tank, and altars. Unfortunately, not much is known about the history of the sanctuary. The Sarapieion C was the official sanctuary, the most important, and covered a large space from north to south on a terrace on the upper part of the tank of Inopos. It was close to the Sanctuary of the Syrian deities. The sanctuary was divided into two parts. A trapezoidal space with a paved road framed by altars and small sphinxes covers the south part. At the north, there is a paved court which is surrounded by cultic buildings: temples dedicated to Isis, Serapis, Anubis, and other buildings. Delos is the site that has offered the largest number of inscriptions dedicated to the Egyptian deities outside Egypt. These inscriptions reveal essential information on the offices; the sanctuary was served by a priest, a keykeeper, a νεωκόρος chosen among the citizens, an ἀρεταλόγος who proclaimed the miracles of the god, an ὄνειροκτίτης who interpreted the dreams etc. The same inscriptions enlighten on the customs and rules that devotees had to follow: wine was forbidden for the worshipers of Isis and Osiris, wool clothes were not allowed for the worshipers of Serapis. The inscriptions also suggest that the deities were venerated under numerous forms: Isis Hathor, Isis close to the Mother of Gods Astarte, Isis Tyche, Isis Aphrodite, Isis Nike, Isis protector of maritime activities, Isis Dikaiosyne.

Date Range: 230 BCE - 60 BCE

Region: Delos

Region tags: Europe, Greece, Aegean

The island of Delos is near the center of the Cyclades archipelago and one of the most important mythological, historical, and archaeological sites of Greece. Among the sanctuaries discovered on the island, three sanctuaries dedicated to the Egyptian deities were brought to light.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Roussel, P. 1916. *Les Cultes égyptiens à Délos du IIIe au Ier siècle av. J.-C.* Nancy: Berger-Levrault.
- Source 2: Baslez, M.-F. 1977. *Recherches sur les conditions de pénétration et de diffusion des religions orientales à Délos (IIIe-1er s. av. notre ère).* Paris: Ecole normale supérieure de jeunes filles.
- Source 3: Bruneau, P. 1970. "Recherches sur les cultes de Delos à l' époque hellénistique et à l' époque impériale." In *Recherches sur les cultes de Delos à l' époque hellénistique et à l' époque impériale.* Paris: E. de Brocard.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odyseus.culture.gr/h/3/gh352.jsp?obj_id=2371
- Source 1 Description: Official website of the Ministry of Culture on Delos
- Source 2 URL: <https://mykonos.gr/dilos/>
- Source 2 Description: Official website of the Municipality of Mykonos

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1873-today

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Directed by the French Archaeological School

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Water source

Notes: The sanctuaries are situated in an uphill area, towards the mountain of the island. Therefore, all structures were built on terraces. In addition, water is an important feature of the Isiac cult. The accessibility to water was achieved by the construction of water tanks, fulfilling both ritual and practical purposes.

- ↳ Type of elevation
 - Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Terracing
 - Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Notes: The sanctuary is situated just outside the inhabited area of Delos, towards the mountain, at the site where other sanctuaries were also situated.

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Notes: Delos was one of the most important Hellenistic ports in the Aegean and the sanctuary was situated at a distance of 950 meters from the port.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

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↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: Several structures survive for each of the three sanctuaries

↳ One single feature

– Water channel

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The inscription RICIS 202/0101 attests at least three generations involved in the Serapeion A

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The temple of Isis was built at the beginning of the second century BCE and then reconstructed by the Athenians in 135 BCE. The same temple has been restored today.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The doric temple of Isis has been reconstructed in recent years

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Serapis, Anubis, Harpocrates, Osiris, Bubastis

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Serapis, Anubis, Harpocrates, Osiris, Bubastis

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: The first sanctuary was created by an individual. Evidence is not clear on the other two sanctuaries

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

Notes: Information is given only for Serapeion A.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specify

–Other [specify]: Revealed in a dream

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Water tanks were created in order to use water coming from a nearby water source

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: There are some structures made of marble.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuaries were decorated with wooden, stone, or textile dedications, statues, reliefs, and altars. The statues would represent the deities, in either Hellenized forms - such as Harpocrates holding a cornucopia and bringing his index to his mouth - and Egyptianizing forms - such as the cynocephalus Anubis and the sphinxes.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Statues, reliefs, dedicated objects would all decorate the sanctuaries. Some were gifts from the devoted; others were part of the sanctuary's construction (for example, the dromos with the sphinxes in Serapeion C).

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Sphinxes were also decorating Serapeion C

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Anubis is represented as a jackal-headed god

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of Isis, Serapis, Anubis have been found

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Representations of ears dedicated to the Theoi Epikooi have been found in the sanctuary

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There are representations of human or divine footprints dedicated to the sanctuary

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The research has not revealed paintings, but it is possible that originally the temples would host such a decoration which did not survive through the centuries.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The RICIS 202/0101 is a characteristic example of an inscription that explains how the cult arrived on the island, who was responsible and how the cult evolved during the following generations.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: Delos is the site that has provided the research with the highest number of inscriptions outside Egypt. Of a total of 438 inscriptions, the majority of them are

dedications towards Isis, Serapis, Anubis, and the other synnaoi theoi.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: no

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The representation of the gods follows the iconographic features known in general from the Mediterranean that characterize the Isiac deities such as Isis with the Isiac knot, Anubis as a jackal-headed god, Isis in the iconographic type of Isis à la voile, etc.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Anubis is represented as a jackal-headed god

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Dedications were a way to thank the gods for listening to their prayers and fulfilling their wishes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Mainly poultry but also small ruminants and pigs. The handling of the victims differed according to the species: the cocks and hens were consecrated whole while only parts of the sheep and the pigs were offered.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: The devoted would offer wooden, stone, or textile dedications, statues, temples, and altars. The representations on the reliefs and statues would portray the gods or other symbols such as footprints or ears. In other cases, they would just offer a dedication written on stone.

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↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Not necessarily

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There is also a cylindrical thesaurus created to accept the donations of the devoted, accompanied by an inscriptio attesting to the name of the dedicator and mentioning that it was dedicated to Serapis, Isis and Anubis.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Probably

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There were permanent offices in the sanctuary except for the priests who would probably be charged with maintenance activities both of the buildings and sculptures.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: It is considered that people who would dedicate the footprints but also ears and other kinds of dedications were devoted visiting the sanctuary in order to fulfill their vow.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably but not ordinarily.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Some inscriptions refer to benches probably used for these purposes.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: There is no direct evidence of festivals on the island of Delos. Nevertheless, the maritime character of Isis - evident mainly due to reliefs with Isis-with-a-sail-type and inscriptions evoking her a Euploia and Soteira - might suggest the celebration of the Navigium Isidis at the beginning of the maritime activities of the year, in March.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Only initiates

Notes: The Navigium Isidis included a procession ending to the port. In that case, all people were welcome to follow the event. There are, though, parts of the procession that addressed only to the initiates. Whether this is the case of Delos as well, as known from other Greek Isiac sanctuaries, such as from Tithorea, is not certain.

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field doesn't know

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Incubation

– Yes

Notes: Probably, as this is the case in other Isiac sanctuaries. The healing activities are ascertained due to the presence of the word *θεραπωντες* in the inscriptions coming from the sanctuary.

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Rituals would include the festivities such as the Navigium Isidis and sacrifices (mainly of fowls, as the osteoarchaeological research has shown). In addition, it is considered that even the dedication of objects in the sanctuary, such as the footprints, and the daily routines regarding the adorning of the cult statue would constitute a ritual.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - No
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Probably some priests, or people holding other offices such as the zakoroi, would work daily in the sanctuary.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Other people would participate only in the processions and were not needed on an everyday basis.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the offices were held by men. Nonetheless, there are some offices, such as the κανηφόροι were women.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: The first priest arrived from Egypt. Except for that, in the following centuries, it is not clear where the priests came from.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: In the majority of the cases, the people who held an office, they were chosen for a specific time period.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Hélène Brun , Martine Leguilloux. Rituels sacrificiels et offrandes animales dans le Sarapieion C de Délos. (Gunnel Ekroth , Jenny Wallensten, Ed.), *Bones, behaviour and belief The zooarchaeological evidence as a source for ritual practice in ancient Greece and beyond*. Stockholm: Skrifter utgivna av Svenska Institutet i Athen.

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